

EFFECTIVENESS OF FLOOD EARLY WARNING SYSTEM IN THE AFFECTED COMMUNITIES OF KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: This paper evaluates the effectiveness of Flood Early Warning system in the affected communities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa were selected as the study to achieve the objectives. The key objectives of this research paper to review the flood situation and existing flood early warning system and its role in flood management in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. To assess and analyze the perspectives of local experts and communities in the four affected communities (Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera and D. I Khan) regarding the success and failures of early warning system. Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. The primary sources are includes sampling, interviews and FGDs. The secondary data sources are stakeholders, line agencies PMD, FFD, NDMA, PDMA, DDMA and local administration in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The major findings highlights the proportion of communities not receiving warnings from 53% to 60%, indicating serious gaps in warning outreach. Similarly, Charsadda and Nowshera showed high agricultural land exposure (22–25%), while D.I. Khan had 15% crops and animals at risk, threatening rural livelihoods. The effectiveness of FEW in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa can be improved by solving these issues faced by the flood management organizations and line agencies to improve FEWS in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Key Words: Flood, Flood early warning, warning dissemination, flood risk management.

1. Introduction

Worldwide flood early warning is very important for monitoring of flood hazard to minimize the impacts of flood (Cammerer et al., 2013). Flood Early warning (FEW) is one of the non-structural measures to reduce damages caused by flood (Ahmed, 2020). Effective flood forecasting and early warning systems (FEWS) are vital components of climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction strategies, enabling agencies and communities to anticipate flood events and take timely action to reduce loss of life and property (Salgado, 2025).

The application of FEW technologies are increasingly and widely adopted by the countries exposed to recurrent flood events (UNISDR, 2022). The potential advantages of advanced FEWS to increase the time span for risk communication and emergency response action (Demeritt and Nobert, 2014). At several spots, a

localized and at few locations regional Flood Early warning system is available, but that needs to be well-connected at global scale to minimize the impacts of flood (Rahman and Shaw, 2014). For a reliable EWS three basic criteria, accurateness, consistency, and suitability are used (WMO, 2022). Early Warning (EW) is one of the main constituents of flood reduction measures, which reduce the economic loss (Basha et al., 2008).

Pakistan is greatly affected by the hydrological and meteorological disasters in history (Rahman and Shaw, 2015). The devastating flood of 2010 was the history worst flood that caused almost two-thousand fatalities, injuries, sources of livelihood earnings, infrastructures and millions of people were displaced (Mustafa & Wrathall, 2011). Till, 2005 the government rely on reactive approaches, but after the earthquake of 2005 a paradigm shift occurred and the

approach was changed from reactive to proactive approach. For this purpose Pakistan adopted different structural and non-structural measures in order to minimize the impacts of these natural disasters. In present scenario flood forecasting and early warning system is one of the important non-structural measures to reduced the flood risk in the flood prone areas of Pakistan.

This paper is an important attempt to evaluate the effectiveness of FEWS and its role in flood management in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Evaluation is particularly important for FEWS in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, due to its vulnerability to flooding. This research paper is divided into five sections. The first section deals with the detail introduction of the study, the second section were given to the methods and material used to carry out the study. Section three discuss the analysis and results. Sections four were given to discussion. On the basis of the analysis result and discussion recommendations are given to make FEWS more effective in the sample districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

2. Materials and Method

The research methodology to conduct this research is composed of five key steps: (1) To review the flood situation and existing FEWS and its role flood management in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan; (2) To assess and analyze the perspectives of local experts and communities in the four affected communities that includes district (Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera, and Dera Ismail Khan) regarding the success and failures of early warning system; (3) To highlights the challenges faced by the existing EWS, that hinder its effectiveness in mitigating

the impact of flood; (4) to identify gaps and weaknesses in the existing FEWS (5) to improve the effectiveness of FEWS and its role in flood management in the study area and recommendations for effectiveness as shown in Figure.1. To analyse the research objectives data were collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Total four communities were surveyed, in district Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera and D.I Khan. In each sample community 10% of the households were surveyed and FGDs were conducted with elderly people, community representatives and key informants in the study area to cross check the data. Secondary data about all the selected variables were collected from the local related organizations.

The existing Flood Early Warning System (FEWS) framework in Pakistan reveals that, despite the presence of institutional frameworks and technical mechanisms, the system effectiveness in reducing flood impacts remains limited. The analysis shows that FEWS plays a critical role in flood management by supporting early detection, forecasting, and dissemination of warnings; however, these functions are unevenly implemented across regions. In flood-prone areas such as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, inadequate coverage of hydro-meteorological stations, limited Doppler radar reach, and challenges posed by complex terrain reduce the accuracy and timeliness of flood forecasts. As a result, warnings often fail to reach vulnerable communities in time, limiting their ability to evacuate and protect lives and property. This highlights a significant gap between the technical capacity of FEWS and its practical effectiveness at the community level.

Figure.1. Research Framework

2.1 Existing FEWS in Pakistan

PMD has a wide network of radar system and weather observatories, which provide data for FF&EWS in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The PMD has installed 10 cm Doppler radars to enhance its weather forecasting and monitoring capabilities. This radar system provides quantitative and three-dimensional precipitation data in catchment areas of main reservoirs, enabling the PMD to better predict and manage floods. The Flood Forecasting Division (FFD), Lahore helps the nation by improving meteorological and hydrological services to produce timely and accurate flood forecasts and warning. Further research and implementation of effective FEWS can help save lives and reduce the economic impact of floods in the effected communities of KP Pakistan.

2.2 Analysis and views of the line agencies and local experts

The analysis and views of local experts and communities are crucial in understanding the effectiveness of Flood Early Warning System (FEWS) in Pakistan. In the study area questionnaires were filled at community level from effected community members to collect data about FEW and dissemination in time. Three FGDs meeting were led with stakeholders and effected communities to validate the data, which were collected during field visit in the affected communities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. After data collection, data were analyzed by using different statistical tools to evaluate the effectiveness and expected outcomes to make FFEW in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa more effective to

minimize the flood risks. According to local experts and communities perceived the FEWS as effective in providing timely warnings, but there were issues with the dissemination of warnings and response capacity as well. Local experts in the field survey have highlight the weaknesses of FEWS in Pakistan. According to the opinion of the local experts, the emphasized the need for improving the accuracy and reliability of FEW, as well as enhancing community engagement and awareness in the affected communities. The analysis and views of local experts and communities are essential in understanding the effectiveness of FEWS in Pakistan. By addressing the challenges and improving the technical capacity, community engagement, and infrastructure development, FEWS can be made more effective in reducing the impact of floods in the affected communities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

2.3 Selection of the affected communities and their profile

In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, four affected communities were selected due to its vulnerability to flooding and more population affected by flood. The affected community districts were selected due to number of reasons. These affected communities districts are located in active flood prone regions, which is affected by flood especially 2010 and 2022 flood, having more population, the major rivers are passing through these communities, more population centers which make it vulnerable for flood as shown in Figure, 2.

Figure. 2. Sample districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

District Swat was selected as affected community, due to its vulnerability to flooding, location, geography, climate and river Swat flood. Floods in district Swat have significant impacts on communities, infrastructure, and the economy. District Charsadda were selected because its location, vulnerability to flooding and river Kabul passing through this region make it more vulnerable to flooding. The climate of Nowshera district is hot in summer and cold in winter, which make it vulnerable to flooding. Similarly, river Kabul and river Indus passing through this region make it more vulnerable to flooding. D. I. Khan is a relevant case study area for flood forecasting and early warning systems due to its vulnerability to flooding. District D.I Khan is prone to flooding due to its location near the Indus river. District D.I Khan is one of the most flood-vulnerable district. Floods in district D.I Khan have significant impacts on communities, infrastructure, and the economy. These four districts are selected as the sample affected communities due to its location, geography, climate and population, which is more vulnerable to flood.

2.4 Questionnaire and data collection in the affected communities

To collect data about FEW questionnaire were arrange for individual and Focused Group

Discussions (FGDs) for the line agencies and Government departments also that deals with flood and EWS in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. According to 2017 Census the population of the sample districts Swat was (2,687,384), Charsadda (1,835,504), Nowshera (1,740,705) and Dera Ismail Khan (1,829,811), which make these districts more vulnerable to floods. For validation of data minimum 213 sample were required. Thus sample were collected according to population more affected in the flood communities off the sample districts, which are 77 household in district Swat, 45 in district Charsadda, 53 in Nowshera district and 38 in D.I Khan district. Five FGDs were arranged with stakeholders to validate the data and information to make FEW in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa more effective to minimize the flood risks.

3. Analysis, results and discussion

PMD is responsible for providing meteorological service in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has a network of hydro-meteorological stations, which provide rainfall, river flows and discharge data. The Early Warning dissemination in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is robust and effective, with warning disseminated through various channels, including mobile phones and media

applications. However, the FFEW in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa covered vast area, which limits its effectiveness. Similarly, the existing radar system not covered the upper Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, which effects the flood warning. The existing FFEW in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is inadequate, due to limited hydro-meteorological stations, communication and dissemination system. Similarly, inadequate flood infrastructure, insufficient reservoir capacity, inaccurate flood risk assessment, limited flood-forecasting, limits FEW efficiency respond to flood.

3.1. Flood Early Warning System in sample districts received or not

In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, FEWS effectiveness varies across different districts. In some districts, FEWS has been successful in providing timely warning to communities, enabling them to evacuate and take necessary precautions. In other districts, however, FEWS has faced significant challenges, including limited infrastructure, inadequate resources, and lack of community engagement. These challenges have compromised the effectiveness of FEWS, leading

to delayed or inaccurate warnings, which can have devastating consequences for communities. In districts (Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera and Dera Ismail Khan) FEWS has been relatively ineffective in providing warnings to communities. These affected districts have faced significant challenges. The districts are prone to frequent flooding, and the existing FEWS infrastructure is often inadequate to provide timely warning to communities living in these districts.

The effectiveness of FEWS also depends on the level of community engagement and participation. In districts where communities are actively involved in the development and implementation of FEWS, the system is more likely to be effective. During survey, the data was collected in the selected districts and communities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. It was found from the analysis that majority of the communities in the flood-prone districts did not receive any warning about last floods 2010 and 2022, which is major challenge for the flood communities in the study area in (Table, 1; Figure, 3).

Table 1, Dissemination of FF&EWS in the sample districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

Ser No	Sample Districts	Flood characteristics	Population 2023	Dissemination of Flood Early Warning in %	
				Yes	No
1.	Swat	Flash Flood	2,687,384	45	55
2.	Charsadda	Riverine Flood	1,835,504	47	53
3.	Nowshera	Riverine Flood	1,740,705	44	56
4.	D. I. Khan	Riverine Flood	1,829,811	40	60

Source: (Field survey, 2022)

Figure. 3 Dissemination of FF&EWS in the sample districts

The district Swat is one of the flood affected area due to elevation from 732 m in south to over 5,000 m above sea level in the north, that makes early warning dissemination due to which it is difficult to give warning in time as shown in Figure, 4. a). The total area of district Swat is about 5,337 km². Due to elevation, rough terrain and topography it is very difficult to disseminate flood early warning. In order to collect data about the flood hazard that settlements are

exposed to flood. The flood management authorities monitor the flood situation in population centres along the river Swat and its tributaries as shown in Figure, 4 b). To analyse the flood in district Swat the data were collected in the affected urban and rural centres in order to identify the flood-affected settlement. The settlement, which were affected are Shamozai, Utror, Balakot, Mingora, Kabbal, Charbagh and KhwazaKhela.

The district Charsadda elevation from 289 m in south to over 804 m above sea level in the north in Figure, 5 a). The dissemination of flood information in time is easy, but due to plain area it is exposed to flood that cause significant damages. The floods have caused widespread destruction, damaging homes, roads, bridges, and agricultural lands. Many communities have been displaced, and thousands of people have been affected due to its location. Most of the settlement in district Charsadda are located in active flood plain of river Kabul and its tributaries which make it more vulnerable to

flood in Figure, 5 b). The tehsils of Charsadda, Shabqadar, and Tangi have been particularly affected, with reports of extensive damage to infrastructure and crops. The floods have also contaminated water sources, posing health risks to the affected population. Dagai Mukaram Khan village was particularly affected. Additionally, Darazak village, Shabqadar Tehsil, when heavy rains triggered floods were affected by flood. Flood forecasting and early warning systems in Charsadda are crucial due to the district vulnerability to flooding.

The district Nowshera elevation from 1407 m in south to over 260m above sea level in the north in Figure, 6 a). District Nowshera has faced significant flood damages. The floods have caused widespread destruction, damaging homes, roads, bridges, and agricultural lands. Many communities have been displaced, and thousands of people have been affected. The settlement located near the Kabul river, Indus river and its tributaries are affected by flood as

shown in Figure, 6 b). The tehsils of Nowshera, Pabbi, and Jehangira have been particularly affected, with reports of extensive damage to infrastructure and crops. The 2010 and 2022 flood in Nowshera heavy monsoon rains caused the river Kabul to overflow, inundating large areas of the district. The floodwaters damaged homes, infrastructure, agricultural lands, displacing thousands of people and economic losses.

The D. I Khan district lies in southern part of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province elevation from 1127 m in south to over 1260 m above sea level in the north in Figure, 7 a). D.I Khan geography and location make it more vulnerable to flood most the settlement of D.I Khan are located near the river Indus and its tributaries as shown in figure 7, b). District D.I Khan has faced significant flood damages. Many communities

have been displaced, and thousands of people have been affected. The tehsils of Dera Ismail Khan, Paharpur, Paroa, and Kulachi have been particularly affected, with reports of extensive damage to infrastructure and crops. The floods have also contaminated water sources, posing health risks to the affected population. Relief efforts have been launched to provide assistance to those in need.

3.2 Understanding of FEWS by the affected communities in sample districts

The flood early warning system in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, categorizes into five flood risks levels which are include very low, low, moderate, high, and very high. This lack of understanding can lead to delayed or inadequate responses to flood warning, resulting in increased risk of damage and loss. Therefore, it

is essential to educate the communities and aware the affected population about the flood early warning system and its different categories to ensure effective flood risk management in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. To know about flood forecasting and early warning system the flood early warning dissemination has been categorized into different categories.

Figure. 8, a) District Swat; b) District Charsadda ; c) District Nowshera); d) District D.I Khan

During survey, the data was collected in the selected districts and communities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, about the understanding of FEWS. Majority of the respondents have answered that the understanding of FEWS is very low as which shows the ineffectiveness of FEWS in the affected districts as shown in (Figure, 8). Similarly, the respondents also answered that the sources of flood early warning dissemination is not updated, that's why people living in sample districts did not received early warning dissemination information properly.

3.3 Effectiveness of FEWS in the sample districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Based on the survey the data were collected in KP Province. To know about FEW data were analyzed to know about the effectiveness the effectiveness of flood. The analysis shows that the sample districts, which receive warning, is not more effective to evacuate population with in time. Similarly, the sample districts received warning is not effective to mitigate flood hazard. Other issues in the sample districts when the warning is received it sometime more effective, effective, early warning somewhat effective and early warning not effective as shown in (Figure, 9).

Figure. 9, a) District Swat; b) District Charsadda ; c) District Nowshera); d) District D.I Khan

3.4 Challenges faced by institutions and communities in effective early warning

The analysis shows the challenges faced by the institution. It was found from the analysis, that 70% of respondents had limited access to information, that they did not have a clear understanding of flood risk and evacuation procedures, which shows that there is a need for improved flood warning communication systems, including more effective dissemination of warnings, increased access to advance technology and enhanced community awareness and preparedness. The survey also shows important implications for flood risk management and disaster preparedness in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Different agencies and stakeholders may not be well-coordinated, leading to confusion and delays. Limited resources and funding compromise the effectiveness of early warning systems. Inadequate infrastructure hinder the collection and dissemination of warning information. Early warning systems may not be tailored to the needs and context of local communities, reducing their

effectiveness. By addressing these institutional challenges, effective early warning systems can be established, saving lives and reducing the impact of flood. By addressing these challenges, it is possible to reduce the vulnerability of communities to floods in the affected communities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

4. Discussion

Flood early warning system is one of the non-structural measure applied to reduce the impacts of floods. These strategies are adopted widely to mitigate the impacts of flood. (FEW) and timely response able the communities to take necessary with in time.

The study shows that the four affected communities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are highly susceptible to floods due to its geographical, river Swat, river Indus and more population. Evaluation of FEWS in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is important for effective flood management.

A majority of flood-affected communities in Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera, and D.I. Khan did not receive early flood warnings during the 2010

and 2022 floods. The proportion of communities not receiving warnings ranged from 53% to 60%, indicating serious gaps in warning outreach. FEWS performance varies spatially; it functions better in some areas but remains ineffective in upper and remote regions, especially mountainous areas like Swat. The large geographical coverage of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and difficult terrain significantly reduce warning effectiveness. Existing Doppler radar systems do not cover upper Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, resulting in delayed or inaccurate flood forecasting. Most respondents reported very low understanding of flood warning categories (very low to very high risk). Poor awareness reduces the ability of communities to take timely protective actions, even when warnings are issued. Human life and housing are the most critical elements at risk across all districts. The proportion of communities not receiving warnings ranged from 53% to 60%, indicating serious gaps in warning outreach. Floods severely affect agricultural land, crops, livestock, and forests. Charsadda and Nowshera showed high agricultural land exposure (22–25%), while D.I. Khan had 15% crops and animals at risk, threatening rural livelihoods. Even where warnings were received, they were frequently described as late, unclear, or only somewhat effective, limiting evacuation and risk reduction. Early warnings did not consistently translate into timely evacuation or damage mitigation. The proportion of communities not receiving warnings ranged from 53% to 60%, indicating serious gaps in warning outreach. This restricted access significantly reduces the reach and effectiveness of FEWS. Weak coordination among line agencies and stakeholders causes delays and confusion. Insufficient funding, outdated infrastructure, and lack of locally tailored warning messages undermine system effectiveness. The current FF&EWS in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is inadequate to meet the needs of highly vulnerable communities. Limitations in forecasting, infrastructure, community awareness, and dissemination mechanisms increase flood risk and losses. By strengthening FEWS, in the flood vulnerable communities the flood damages should be reduced in the vulnerable communities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

5. Conclusion

The study analyzed the effectiveness of the FEWS in the affected communities of district Swat, Charsadda, Nowshera and D.I Khan of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. To address the FF&EWS challenges, it is recommended that the government invest in modern communication technologies, such as mobile applications and social media, to disseminate flood warnings more quickly and widely. Similarly, proper dissemination and communication among line agencies that include PMD, NDMA, PDMA, and DDMA with affected communities can make flood early warning more effective in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. By addressing the challenges, Pakistan can develop more effective flood forecasting and early warning system, to reduce the impacts of flood in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

The study finds that while flood forecasting and early warning systems exist in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, their coverage, accessibility, community understanding and operational effectiveness are insufficient, particularly in highly flood-prone districts. Strengthening monitoring infrastructure, expanding radar coverage, improving community awareness, and enhancing institutional coordination are essential to reduce flood impacts and save lives.

Declaration of Interest:

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this research paper.

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